

GREEN HYBRID BIO BATTERY FROM WASTEWATER, PLANTS, FRUITS, RECYCLING OLD BATTERIES AND LEATHER WASTES

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Abstract

Every day huge amounts (approximately 1 Ton from each tannery) of collagen from waste chrome shavings is generated in India from tanneries. These chrome shavings can be used to prepare collagen and many value added products. A study was made to use collagen from chrome shaving wastes as an alternate energy source natural electrolyte binder to produce DC Voltage in bio battery. Chrome shavings are hydrolyzed to make collagen paste. Separately, collagen fiber is thermally degraded to gelatin paste which is mixed with collagen paste; garlic nanoparticles, onion nanoparticles, aluminum paste, and conducting gel and conducting ink to form electrolyte paste. The electrolyte paste in association with copper and zinc electrodes, or, carbon and zinc electrodes work as bio battery anode and cathode, the electrolyte has been characterized using FTIR, SEM, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA). Results show encouraging trends for commercial exploitation of the facility.

Keywords:

Bio energy, Collagen paste, Plant nanoparticles, Fruit waste, Waste Batteries, Natural electrolyte.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Recycling and Reusing of the wastes in these areas pose threats because of the polluted and toxicity of the land and the water near the cities. The people are affected when consumed foods grown in these land and water [1].

In many cases cleaning by evacuation of these toxicants and pollutants result in expensive treatments. Many cases of instances show less toxicities and pollution and may require a scientific approach to remediate and widely it is known as "Recycling and reusing of waste organic, inorganic, bio materials and other recyclable materials for making bio batteries (BB) and value added products". Biomaterials' recycling is defined as a process that uses biological materials such as green plants or their enzymes, nanoparticles to retain the natural environment changed by toxins, pollutants, and contaminants to its original condition. Biomaterial recycling is an easy method of recycling that can be easily understood, followed, and can be trained to any common man

with or without proper education and cost effective eco-friendly in nature. There is a great potential for the biomaterials recycling and sustainability when linked with the economic growth prospects, will lead to green jobs in small scale industries in biomaterials recycling for bio energy and ecological regeneration. Few examples are recycling and reusing tannery-based leather wastes, chrome shavings, plant leaves-based nanoparticles for bio energy and solar cells applications using silica nanoparticles from waste plant leaves. The nanotechnology-based biomaterials recycling has limitations in environmental conditions [2]. Therefore, recent advances in biomaterial recycling for the treatment of biological wastes and biomaterials waste using different treatment technologies are essential for these industries. In this century of innovative technologies in the biomaterials recycling and reusing. Using waste biomaterials, enzymes, waste antibacterial plant leaves and nanoparticles, recycling and reusing methodologies would be applied which have been proved as anti-toxicant

and biomaterials recycling agents of pollution and hybrid green bio energy. The sandwiched bioinformatics simulation methodology easy to design, develop with the nanoparticles, makes them innovative technologies for suitable and, sustainable biomaterials recycling and reusing.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Bio Battery

i. The Basic Bio Battery

The bio battery consists of Zinc Cathode and Copper Anode using collagen with PEG, plant extracts as carbon nanoparticles makes the electrolyte. The 40 ml electrolyte produces 1.25 volts DC and 900 m A current =1.125W Per Cell.

ii. Collagen Based Bio Batteries

1 kg of collagen paste with 1 litre of water was taken, Polyethylene Glycol 100 ml and diluted sulphuric acid of 300 ml is mixed to form the electrolyte having a pH slightly more than 5. Later 5 gm. carbon nanoparticles added to 90 ml, then thoroughly mixed and the solution is the electrochemical bio battery electrolyte.

iii. Chemical Structure of Collagen

[Chemical Formula 1]

Fig.1. Chemical structure of Collagen.

Fig.2. TEM of Onion carbon nanoparticles [3].

Fig. 3. Chemical structure of PEG

iv. Chemical Structure of Carbon from Onion And Garlic Plants

Fig. 4. Chemical structure of onion carbon.

B. Flow chart of Collagen Making

Fig. 5. Flow chart for making collagen and electrolyte paste.

A Onion (Spherical Onion nanoparticle with the size in the range of 40 to 50nm) and carbonaceous nano particles of onion were procured from the local market. Leather wastes were collected from CLRI premises. The wastes were cut into pieces using a cutting machine. These leather pieces were then immersed in dilute sulphuric acid. The collagen from leather was thus extracted. Then the collagen was added to the conducting gel. Then *Moreingo oliefera lam* leaves powder along with the gel were added to 5% PolyEthylene Glycol. Then this solution was mixed with silver paste and onion nano particles. Thus obtaining the electrolyte paste.

Preparation of Plant Extracts (*moringa oleifera lam*)

Moringaoleifera lam leaves were collected from CLRI premises. These leaves were sun dried, powdered, and added to electrolyte to make paste. Electrolyte was prepared at Biological material pilot plant, CLRI.

III EXPERIMENTATION

2.0 g of weighed dried powder of *moringaoleifera lam* leaves was treated with 12ml of concentrated HNO₃ and boiled till brown fumes ceased. After cooling, 2ml of double distilled water was added and 4ml of H₂O₂ to decompose the organic layer. Further it was heated till effervescence ceased and after cooling, the step was repeated. After that distilled water was added to the solution and boiled. This was used for estimation. Fresh leaves of moringa oleifera lam were taken and sundried then powdered. Then made to an electrolytic paste. The prepared electrolytic paste was observed for pH. The pH value obtained was 5. Then the electrolytic paste was filled in series of containers and connected with electrodes and battery. The voltage generated was 17.4 V DC. The electrolyte paste can generate electricity up to 100mA with 1.5V which can be seen by connecting an LED lamp of the range [4].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table1. Series connectivity of electrolyte paste in 40 well plates. Used as button cells.

C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10
2.3 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv					
C11	C12	C13	C14	C15	C16	C17	C18	C19	C20
2.3 mv	2.4 mv	2.3 mv	2.3 mv	2.4 mv	2.3 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv
C21	C22	C23	C24	C25	C26	C27	C28	C29	C30
2.4 mv	2.3 mv	2.4 mv	2.3 mv	2.3 mv	2.3 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv
C31	C32	C33	C34	C35	C36	C37	C38	C39	C40
2.3 mv	2.4 mv	2.3 mv	2.4 mv	2.3 mv	2.3 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv	2.4 mv

From Table 1 it was observed that the electrolyte paste filled in 40 well plates can generate voltage between the range of 2.3mV to 2.4mV each.

Fig.6.Electrolyte paste filled well plates connected in series and parrallel method. 31.6 DC V produced.

Fig.7. The 20 ml electrolyte bio battery.

In figure 6,The electrolyte paste was filled in both series and parallel wellplates.(84x2). It was observed that this can generate a voltage of 31.6 V DC. In fig 7, The electrolyte paste was used as bio battery of 20 ml and it generated 1.25V, 1000mA and 1.25W per cell.0.0625 W per ml.

The study revealed that 2 grams of the moringa oleifera lam leaf powder extract has 14.30% of iron content

Fig.8. Bio batteries connected in series produced 17.4 V DC and 1.025 A, Powering 3 W LED lamp.

40 ml of each 12 Bio batteries connected in series produced 17.4 V DC and 1.025 A current per pack of 12 batteries connected in series. As per the concentration of the electrolyte and it's ingredients such as PEG, nano particle, conducting gel, aluminium paste, waste battery materials (i.e) nickel and cadmium in very small quantity (2gm), in order to recycle the waste battery material and protect the environment from pollution.

FTIR spectroscopy

The basic theory of Fourier-Transform Infrared spectroscopy is that the bonds between different elements absorb light at different frequencies. The light is measured using an infrared spectrometer which produces the output of an infrared spectrum. The IR spectrum is a graph of infrared light absorbance by the substance on the vertical axis and the frequency (wavelength) on the horizontal axis. FTIR analysis measures the range of wavelengths in the infrared region that are absorbed by a material. This is accomplished through the application of infrared radiation (IR) to samples of a material. The sample's absorbance of the infrared light's energy at various wavelengths is measured to determine the material's molecular composition and structure.

FTIR analysis

Fig.9. FTIR analysis: The FTIR spectra of Onion nano particles[14].

Sharp peaks at 1513 cm^{-1} are due to $\text{C}=\text{C}$. Absorption bands at around $1457, 1243$ and 1037 cm^{-1} are attributed to $-\text{C}-\text{H}-$ and $-\text{C}-\text{C}-$ bending modes.

On connecting the Batteries in Series and Parallel connections, we found when the bio batteries are connected in parallel connection and the current generated was 6.6mA . When connected in series connection, they produced 17.4V DC and 1.025A Current per pack powering LED lamps. Further, we studied the Voltage, Current, and Resistance for few available Biomaterials viz., Fruits, Vegetables. Using Copper Anode, Zinc Cathode and Electrolyte. A graph was plotted their Voltage vs. Distance. pH value of the materials was noted at room temperature 32Deg.C . For a tomato-based bio battery 4.4 pH , weighing 40.0 g [5]. On observation, we found the Resistance, Voltage and Current with respect to distance of electrodes and graphs 10, 11 and 12 indicate V, R and I vs. D. Figs. 10, 11 and 12 shows tomato bio battery V, R & I [6].

Fig.10. Graph of Distance of electrodes in cm and Voltage in mV.

Fig.11. Graph of Distance of electrodes in cm and Resistance R in Ohms.

Fig.12. Graph of Distance vs. Current

V. CONCLUSIONS

Interest in plants with antimicrobial properties has been revived as a result of antimicrobial resistance. *Moringaoleifera* Lam is one of the best known, widely distributed and grown species of a monogenetic family *Moringaceae*. It is native to the western and sub-Himalayan parts of Northwest India, Pakistan, and Afghanistan. *Moringaoleifera* lam leaves acts as an antibacterial, antimicrobial and has iron contents which used to vary the resistance of the battery. This electrolyte paste is therefore nontoxic and not contaminated by any microorganism. Onion nano particles act as an antifungal and anti-fouling agent and increased shelf life up to 3 years. Bio battery was tested in different quantities with different pH values at room temperature with different combinations and concentration of electrolyte paste. Waste batteries

can also be recycled and reused using Baking Soda, Citric Acid, Distilled Water and Salt to reduce the pollution. At the end, the following observations were made: The power generated using a single bio-battery 20 ml electrolyte used as bio battery produced 1.25 volts and 1000 m A current and 1.125W Per Cell. An output of 16 V DC, 1000 mA is obtained from 96 well-plates connected in series whereas 36-volt DC, 1200 mA has been obtained from a parallel connection of 96 well-plates using different pH (6) and distance between electrodes reduced (1 cm). Also 40 ml of each 12 Bio batteries connected in series produced 17.4 V DC and 1.025 A current per pack. (12 Cells).

TGA analysis in electrolyte sample

Thermo gram of collagen, single step weight loss from 59 to 213°C and around 96% weight loss is observed. The final residue was found to be 58.26%. Lab scale level.

The denaturation temperature of electrolyte powder determined from DSC curve and is found to be 112.80°C. The bio battery (BB) from waste plants, fruits and recycling old batteries using carbon as anode and zinc as cathode shows improvements in voltage and currents. The redox material used from the waste material along with collagen acts as a good binding material, semiconductor and the electrolyte remain stable for a long time and increased shelf life. Further suitable redox materials with more voltage and current producing materials can be incorporated to increase the gain both in voltage and current there by increasing the power. The plant-based nanoparticles used acts as antibacterial, antifouling, natural, Environment friendly, feasible and cost effective. This study was made at bench scale level randomly, further can be made into lab scale and pilot scale after standardizing.

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Dr. Inbasekaran S, Senior Research Officer, Instrumentation department, CLRI, Chennai, India. Having completed Post-Doctoral degree in bio battery, establishing a remarkable improvement in designing, development, patenting and publishing Bio-Battery at different combinations. Has published 25 papers, authored 1 book and has 3 patents. Also has transferred 1 technology to the industry. Serving as reviewer of many academic journals and has been coordinating many research projects as Investigator from Govt. research funding.

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Dr. Panda is an outstanding Chemical engineer and has contributed significantly in process modeling, identification and control. Modernization of Chemical industry, odor-control & process intensification of chrome chemical sectors with the advent of material handling and chemical engineering inputs have led CSIR-CLRI to greater heights. His teaching and independent research publications in high impact journals are praiseworthy and richly deserve academic recognition. His experiences and concept in process monitoring, optimization, and control in continuous process industries especially in refinery & petrochemicals will be beneficial in any process industry.